

POLITICAL LEXICON (LINGUISTICS) AS A SCIENTIFIC DISCIPLINE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14234532>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 24th November 2024

Accepted: 27th November 2024

Online: 28th November 2024

KEYWORDS

Political linguistics, political communication, political science, sociology, rhetoric, cognitive linguistics, normative approach, multidisciplinary.

ABSTRACT

Today, the researches carried out on studying the problems of sociolinguistics are gaining importance in world linguistics. In this regard, the inadequacy of consistent analyzes of the existing multilingual society in the world and the issues of interaction, perfection, status increase and functional development of different languages in practice, effective in researching the advanced world experience in this direction, applying and conducting sociolinguistic research is one of the important tasks in linguistics. In fact, the parable of the study of the functional capabilities of the language is also a linguistic category that can be studied by today's linguistics. The political lexicon is a social process that requires serious attention to be paid to the modern sociolinguistic direction of social and political phenomena arising on the basis of a number of social demands in the process of globalization of science. The need for sociolinguistic research in science, more precisely, in linguistics, can be seen today in the example of the expansion of any national languages. In this respect, it is necessary to differentiate the social differentiation of the language according to the territorial affiliation of the members of society, social groups according to their profession, occupation, opportunity and territorial origin. In this, the groups of units that are studied in the process of political-lexical analysis of any language are identified, which are, in particular, lexicons related to history, international and labor movements, political and economic terminology, political and legal terminology, a large part of the military lexicon, the lexicon of international negotiations.

The field of political lexicon (now referred to as political linguistics) is one of the relatively new areas of applied linguistics, and this phrase, that is, a scientific term, has been actively used since the 90s of the 20th century. Specialists in this field emphasize that the main direction of activity is the language of international relations related to any political communication framework, as well as the language of political texts serving the international diplomatic corps system [5; 94]. However, no significant recommendations have been developed on how to properly address this political dialogue. This is a big problem, especially for societies with very limited political traditions, because the scientific basis of political style has not yet been developed within a specific language related to the language of the political text.

Political lexicon, more precisely, the language of political communication, is used to promote certain social and political ideas within the country, to have an emotional impact on the citizens of the country and to encourage them to take certain political actions in the direction of the development of society, to develop public approval, social is that it should serve as a speech activity aimed at creating and establishing relationships. It is known that today, at least occasionally, everyone who reads a newspaper, turns on the radio or television becomes the addressee of political communication. When this person goes to referendums and elections held at the national level, he participates in political life and performs this activity without the influence of subjects of political communication. Territorial information should include everything related to the perception and evaluation of political reality in the process of communicative activity. So, society reflects the existing political reality, changes along with it and participates in its change.

Also, the main purpose of the political lexicon is to study various relations between language, thinking, communication, subjects of political activity and the political situation of society, and it creates conditions for developing the optimal strategy and tactics of political activity. Political communication affects the distribution and use of power as it serves as a means of influencing the minds of people who make political decisions (voters, deputies, officials, etc.) [1]. Political communication not only conveys information, but also has an emotional impact on the addressee, changes the political landscape of the world that exists in the human mind.

It seems that the political lexicon is a scientific-popular direction of great practical importance for the society and the individual of the society. Studying the experience of communicative activities in the political sphere will help to develop specific recommendations for political officials, journalists and all specialists in public relations. However, not all citizens in a democratic society have the same strong political communication skills in preparing and understanding speech. Therefore, it should be understood that in order to develop the political tendency of any society, it is necessary to form and develop the political consciousness of the individual of this society. In this case, the political lexicon serves as a program in his political communication. The theoretical and practical analysis of this modern political communication helps to harmonize the communication practice of new generations of political leaders and journalists, as well as the use of world standards in the review of internal political communication helps to form a positive image of the country in foreign public representatives.

In recent decades, the most promising scientific directions often appear in the zone of communication between different fields of knowledge. One such field is political linguistics, which emerged at the intersection of linguistics and political science and took into account the achievements of ethnology, social psychology, sociology and other humanities. The need for the emergence and development of such a new scientific direction is determined by the increasing interest of society in the conditions and mechanisms of political communication [6; 91-93].

Political lexicon, that is, political linguistics, is closely related to other branches of linguistics, it is sociolinguistics dealing with the problems of interaction between language and society. Functional stylistics and especially journalistic and official style, classical and modern rhetoric is an integrative set of a number of disciplines, such as cognitive linguistics and text linguistics.

The political lexicon is fully characterized by the features of modern linguistics such as multidisciplinary (using the methodology of various disciplines), anthropocentrism (human, linguistic person becoming the starting point for the study of linguistic phenomena), expansionism (multidisciplinary) [9]. Political communication is based on the essence of functionalism (the study of language in action, speech, in the implementation of its functions) and explanation (the desire not only to describe the facts, but also to explain them) [9]. In addition, the political lexicon is closely related to the sciences that study personal, social and national consciousness - social psychology, cultural studies, sociology, political science, ethnography.

Modern political linguistics actively participates in the general problems of political communication, analyzes its difference from communication in other areas, problems of political speech genres (slogan, leaflet, program, newspaper article, speech at a rally, parliamentary debate, speech, parliamentary debate, speech, etc.) studies and controls the performance characteristics of political texts [1]. Also, political linguistics actively approaches the problems of idiocy of individual politicians, political parties and trends, considers the strategy, tactics and techniques of political communication, studies the composition, vocabulary and phraseology of political texts, as well as the use of various figurative tools in them.

Among the most important areas of political linguistics are the consideration of specific political concepts within the framework of the relevant language and national culture, solving the problems of understanding the political reality of the state by citizens of other countries, and the comparative study of political relations. This process takes place in different countries and at different stages of social development.

In recent years, political linguistics has become an independent field of linguistic research. Publications belonging to this direction are often reflected in their names, in the formation of research goals and tasks, in defining the topic and object of study, and in describing the material on which the work is based. In some cases, research on political communication is based on diversity in the understanding of political communication, that is, its linguistic and political nature.

First, some authors connect the language of political communication, or rather, its linguistic essence, only with the modern language itself.

Second, materials on the study of political communication are often presented as results of the study of media language [1].

It is known that the political speech intersects with the language of mass media, but it is not always correct to link the publication materials to one or another speech (style). Because other sources of information on linguistics in enriching the speech of political communication include research on speech culture, lexicology and phraseology, theory and practice of journalism, psychology, sociology and political science. Of course, such publications should be taken into account when determining the general trends in the development of political communications of a particular country.

The importance of the diversity of schools and tendencies of modern political linguistics is that it increases the interest in political discourse in itself, and also that it contains the diversity of materials, methods, aspects of analysis and positions characteristic of local science. In our opinion, it is necessary to carry out a number of fundamental research works for the further development of this field, gradually moving from the process of preservation to the stage of development. They can be described in the following system:

1. Description of individual elements of political language in the field of the theory of political linguistics.
2. Chronological scope of the research: (former) Soviet or independence period.
3. Step-by-step analysis of the language or (including vocabulary, phonetics, word formation, morphology, syntax) method of comprehensive study of the text.
4. Normative and descriptive approach (usually critical, analysis from the point of view of compliance with norms with calls to fight against "violation of a specific language"), i.e. clarification and study of new phenomena, as well as criteria for their evaluation.
5. To study the general features of political language.
6. To study the road maps of certain political leaders, political directions and parties, or to study the general patterns of political language.
7. Discursive study of communicative roles, rituals, strategies and tactics, that is, linguistic study of political language.
8. Using psycholinguistics, cognitive linguistics, sociolinguistics, cultural linguistics, structuralism, rhetoric and other language methods in the process of studying political communication.
9. In the process of studying domestic political speech, to determine the general and special features of political speeches of different countries and periods.
10. The need to carry out various researches related to related fields of science.

It should be noted that many publications emphasize the need to use different methods to study political communication [6; 91-93]. This should be supported, because they are normative and descriptive of the news and integrate aspects and consistently explores different language levels and text features, and draws on material from different developmental stages.

One of the most important issues of modern political linguistics is the discursive approach to the study of political texts. Therefore, each concrete text is considered in the context of the political situation in which it was created, its relationship with other texts, taking into account the goals, political views and personal qualities of the author, his unique

perception of this text. It should be considered what role this text can play in the system of political texts and, more broadly, in the political life of the country. For example, the same opinion and even the same statements are taken completely differently in the text of a journalist's newspaper article and in the official statement of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan or the President. In the United States, statements made by the same politician in the heat of the election campaign and after holding an important public office may have a completely different weight.

According to tradition, power is one of the highest social values, and therefore all human capabilities and scientific achievements are used in the struggle for power. Authors of political texts spend a lot of effort to achieve the desired result. Therefore, when analyzing the political communication, the high skill of the authors or their creative poverty, their communicative success and failures are particularly noticeable.

Researches in the field of the language policy of the state, which fall into the sphere of interest of political linguistics and sociolinguistics, focused on the study of political communication, should be distinguished. To simplify it a bit, it means that linguists are concerned with how politicians speak, and language policy makers are concerned with what politicians should do to make optimal use of language. Therefore, the field of political linguistics should include such important work areas as the analysis of operational problems. In particular, the study of other languages of the state and the country (starting with the need for official recognition of the state language), the study of the problems of international communication languages (world languages), as well as the issue of the attitude to the state regulation of graphics. All these problems are related to the state policy in the field of common language use, and they can be solved positively from the framework of political linguistics.

Today, in modern political linguistics, the textual language of the political programs of political parties and its stylistic features, as well as the speeches of individual politicians, are actively studied. In addition, many publications offer using different methods for studying the terms of political communication and their specific aspects. Indeed, combining the normative and descriptive aspects of research, the consistent study of different language levels and text features, and the basis of materials related to different stages of development determine the scientific perspective of science.

The lexicon of political linguistics also relies on a number of political terms. Each of them has its own principles, and they develop based on their own requirements. We will try to briefly describe some of them in this article.

Political language. The issue of the existence of the political language as a special semiotic subsystem within the national language is controversial. According to some scholars, political communication takes place in a very special version of the Uzbek language, which can be called a political language [4; 15-19]. Supporters of the opposite point of view believe that the real linguistic features of the uniqueness of political communication are few insignificant, they do not go beyond the grammatical and even lexical norms of the Uzbek language.

Indeed, the question seems quite reasonable: "Can one of the lexical-phraseological subsystems of the modern literary language be called a "language"?"

However, it is known that colloquial, scientific or official business speech has no less specific characteristics than political speech, and therefore the term “political language” is no less than the term “official business language” that is still used. Therefore, the political language is definitely not a special national language, but a politically oriented version of the national (Uzbek, Russian, English or other language). In recent years, to avoid the loose use of the term language, many experts prefer to talk about the specifics of “scientific speech” or “official business speech”; accordingly, in the study of political texts it is often preferable to speak only of the features of political discourse or political communication.

Political text. In linguistics, a text is a sequence of words (sentences) united by semantic connection, the main properties of which are consistency and integrity. A political text can be of different genres, it can be oral (speech at a rally or parliamentary debate, a speech at a party convention, a television interview with a political leader, etc.) or written (a newspaper article, a pamphlet, a political party program, etc.).

The meaningful feature of the type of texts under consideration is that they reflect the activities of parties, other public organizations, state authorities, public and state leaders and activists, and direct development of the social and economic structure (in the broadest sense).

The objective sign of the political essence of the text is the purpose of influencing the political situation with its help.

It is characterized by the promotion of certain ideas of the society, emotional impact on the citizens of the country and their motivation to political actions, in other words, the political text focuses directly or indirectly on the distribution of political power and its use. Many political texts contain statements of facts and opinions, but such information serves as another piece of evidence to convince the addressee and, ultimately, his political position.

A political context is a piece of text that contains a unit selected for analysis (for example, a word) and is sufficient to determine the meaning of this unit in this text. However, the entity being defined is not part of the context. In some cases, a single sentence is enough to correctly understand the meaning of a certain word, and in others, it is necessary to consider a much larger part of the text, or even the entire text. Based on this, the context is divided into narrow and broad context types. Some experts have a very broad understanding of the concept under consideration and therefore use the terms political context, situational context and extralinguistic context.

Political speech. In linguistics, speech (speech activity) is the process of using language, the result of speech activity is the creation of a text. Accordingly, political speech is the use of a common language in the process of creating a political text. The uniqueness of political speech is determined by its content and issues (distribution of power between states, in the state and its structures), functions (influence on the political landscape of the addressee’s world, emotional impact on the receiver, inclination).

The term “**political communication**” is often used in cases where it is necessary to emphasize the participation of not only the addresser (that is, the speaker or writer), but also the receiver (that is, the listener or reader) in speech activity. In political communication, in contrast to everyday or artistic communication, the subject and addressee of speech activity in most cases is not a person as a person, but a person as a representative of a certain political organization or power structure. For example, many political documents do not have an

official author and are published publicly in the name of an organization, a state structure, accordingly, a speech written by a referee is accepted and analyzed as a presidential speech, and many political documents are signed not by their actual author, but by the head of a political organization or power structure.

Political style of language. Political language style is the speech features of the use of the national language characteristic of a certain politician, a certain political party or organization.

Features of political linguistics can be related to preference for different language tools.

In general, political linguistics uses not only traditional, for example, semantics, various research methods known in the field of studying the meanings of words, but also methods such as content analysis - this is a study method. A large collection of texts is needed to determine the intentions of the authors of these texts, which are not clearly expressed. These intentions are often hidden, and we observe that one thing is said but another is meant.

A bright feature of modern research in the field of political communication is the use of various methodologies. From this point of view, the research conducted using the methods specific to cognitive linguistics, sociolinguistics, cultural linguistics, text linguistics, rhetoric and speech culture stand out.

References:

1. Budaev E. V., Chudinov A. P. "Modern political linguistics" [Electronic resource]. Access mode: URL: <http://philology.ru/linguistics1/budaev-chudinov-06a.htm>.
2. Budaev E.V., Voroshilova M.B. and others. "Modern political linguistics": (a textbook) Yekaterinburg, Urals: state ped, flour 2011.
3. Maslova V. A. "Political linguistics". Yekaterinburg, 2008, pp. 43-48.
4. Nurmonov A. "Methodology and methods of linguistic research". "Akademnashr" publishing house, 2010.
5. Gavrilova, M.V. "Political connection of the 20th century" M.V. Gavrilov. - St. Petersburg: Publishing House of the Nevsky Institute of Language and Culture, 2008. - 94 p.
6. Karpukhina, E.A. "Peculiarities of political speech" / E.A. Karpukhina // Philological sciences. "Questions about theory and practice". Tambov: Diploma, 2011. No. 4 (11). - B. 91-93.
7. Chernikh, A.I. "Media and democracy": / A.I. Chernihiv. - M., St. Petersburg: Universitetskaya kniga, 2011. - 272 p.
8. Cherniavskaya V.E. "Discourse as a phantom object": from text to speech and back? [Electronic resource]. URL: <http://sites.google.com/site/cognitiondiscourse/vypusk-no3-2011/cernavskaa-v-e> (accessed 06/06/2019).
9. Sheigal E.I. "Semiotics of political speech" [Electronic resource]. URL: <http://www.twirpx.com/file/56756/> (Accessed: 06/11/2019).
10. O.K. Хакимбаева. Картина мира и языковая ментальность. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 2022. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=1nUR YUAAAAJ&citation_for_view=1nUR YUAAAAJ:eQOLeE2rZwMC

11. О.К. Хакимбаева. Multidiscipline Proceedings of Digital Fashion Conference, 2022. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=1nUR_YUAAAAJ&citation_for_view=1nUR_YUAAAAJ:WF5omc3nYNoC
12. X.O. Kalandarovna. Expression of Proverbs Reflecting the Social and Physiological Characteristics of Women. Miasto Przyszłości, 2024. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=1nUR_YUAAAAJ&citation_for_view=1nUR_YUAAAAJ:roLk4NBRz8UC